

Garret was in a Car Accident on Saturday
by Brian Paul Kaess

Garret Thomas Kaess recently relayed me this news. On Saturday (August 9, 2025), he was in his vehicle (a car) in Indiana and stopped at a red light, when, all of a sudden, a large Silverado Truck, with a toolbox in the back, suddenly crashed into him in the rear of his vehicle at a fairly high speed, causing the rear window to shatter, with pieces of glass striking Garret in the back of the head, while the rest flew past him. He managed to pull himself from the car, but his vehicle was some sort of wreck!

The driver was a Hispanic male, without a license who may have been in the country illegally. Garret was upset at the scene, but it is not clear if it was a DUI or not. It just felt like one- getting plowed into! I don't know if the paramedics treated him, but Garret sarcastically said, that he has had 'ambulance chasers' (i.e Lawyers) calling him all week. When the police arrived and realized what had happened and that the man did not have a license, they threw him in jail. Garret thinks that ICE will get a call too!

Garret said it has been slow getting insurance to pay, but just give that time I am sure. When I told Mayte, she was just astounded. An onlooker who saw the vehicle couldn't believe Garret wasn't hospitalized. We are grateful, and Thank God that Garret may recover from his injuries. That's all for now.

Garret later said the accident was on Prospect street in Indianapolis about a mile from home. He had stopped behind a car at a red light, and the dude just plowed into him, likely texting or something. Maybe the culprit is in Alligator Alcatraz by now! Since Garret is still walking and made it home, the crows weren't circling overhead just yet! There is yet a clarion of hope.